

Identification And Quantification of Synthetic Food Colours in Marketed Fruit Juices

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ABSTRACT

Synthetic Food Colours (SFCs) are often preferred over natural colours as they are less expensive, more stable, blend more easily, add no flavour and can be used in tiny amounts. This study was carried out to determine the amount of SFCs limit in marketed fruit juices and to bring awareness among the general Public. All selected nine different Synthetic food colours in various marketed fruit juices were identified by Paper chromatography and thin layer chromatography techniques and it was confirmed by their R_f values. Quantification was carried out by UV-Visible spectrophotometric method (Shimadzu UV-1900i) for all 09 SFCs. The absorption maxima of all 09 SFCs were standardized. Linearity was found to be in the concentration range of 0.1-50µg/ml for all 09 SFCs. LOD, LOQ and all Calibration parameters were calculated, and the Correlation coefficient was NLT 0.997. The %RSD value for repeatability, Intraday and Inter day studies was found to be less than 2%. The amount of SFCs present in different marketed fruit juices was calculated and was found to be less than the ADI limit given by US-FDA.

Keywords: SFCs, Colorimetric method, US-FDA guidelines.

INTRODUCTION

Synthetic food colours/Artificial food colours (SFC) are artificial additives used to enhance the visual appearance of food and beverages. SFCs are derived from synthetic chemicals, and they are used worldwide for imparting vibrant colours to their finished products and to avoid the loss of original colour in food, beverages, sweets, cakes and confectionaries etc. to make the products more appealing, alluring, informative and to attract customers¹. SFCs are used instead of natural colours, as they are cheaper, more stable to heat, light and other processing exposures and are mostly water soluble.

Types of Synthetic food colours:

Based on their chemical composition, SFCs are classified into different classes.

1. **AZO DYES:** They are considered the largest group of synthetic food colors and are widely used. They are derived from azo compounds. Azo dye containing compounds include

Tartrazine(E102), Allura Red(E129) and Sunset Yellow(E110).

2. **XANTHENE DYES:** These colors are commonly used in food. It includes colors like Erythrosine (E127).

3. **INDIGOID DYES:** These colors are derived from indigo and its derivatives. One such example is Indigo Carmine (E132).

4. **TRIPHENYLMETHANE DYES:** They are derived from triphenylmethane compounds. They include colors such as Brilliant Blue (E133).

As per US-FDA² and FSSAI³ regulations, nine Synthetic food colours are permitted (4 Red shades (E122, E124, E127), 2 Yellow shades (E102, E110), 2 Blue shades (E132, E133) and one green shade (E143) in limits beyond that they cause many Adverse effects like Allergy, hyperactivity reactions, carcinogenic, genotoxic, and various cancers and neurobehavioral problems etc. Regulatory agencies establish ADI (Acceptable Daily Intake) levels for synthetic food colours, representing the amount that

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can be consumed daily over a lifetime without appreciable health risk. According to data published in many countries, it is observed that coloured food products are major source for food intoxication⁴. SFCs and its metabolites present in marketed fruit juices may produce serious allergic reactions⁵ and several methods⁶⁻⁹ available for detection of SFCs are complicated, time consuming and tedious. A simple TLC, Paper Chromatography and Colorimetric method needs to be developed. In the present study, an attempt was made to identify the different Synthetic food colours present in samples of marketed fruit juices by TLC, Paper chromatography and quantify by UV-Visible Spectrophotometric method and to calculate the amount of SFCs present in the various samples collected from the Market.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Instruments used: Electronic weighing balance(sartorius-TE214S), UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu-1900i, software version-UV-Vis), Ultra sonicator (RC Systems-MU 1700)

Apparatus used: TLC plates, Chromatography paper sheets

Chemicals and reagents used: Ammonium acetate, Acetone, Sodium acetate, Ammonia, Distilled water.

Standards: Nine Synthetic food colours (Allura red, Azorubine/Carmoisine, Ponceau 4R, Erythrosine, Fast green, Tartrazine, Sunset yellow, brilliant blue, Indigo carmine) were purchased from Ases Chemical Works Brahm Bagh, Jodhpur

Samples: Samples of Marketed juices were purchased from different shops, Supermarkets and bazaars in Bangalore, Karnataka.

PRELIMINARY TESTS:

Preliminary test was performed to check the colour and solubility of SFCs (Synthetic food colours) in different reagents. The observations obtained are presented. (Table 1)

PAPER CHROMATOGRAPHY:

Paper chromatography is an analytical technique for separating and identifying substances and mixtures. The main principle involved is partition i.e., partition co-efficient in which the compounds are distributed between 2 liquids (Stationary phase and Mobile phase). The components of the mixture migrate at different rates, and they occupy different positions on the paper.

Stationary Phase: Grade 1 chromatography paper.

Mobile Phase: Sodium acetate (3 gm): Ammonia (10ml): Distilled Water (90 ml)

The movement of substance relative to the solvent is expressed in terms of migration parameter such as R_F . The observations obtained are presented. (Table 2)

THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHY:

The main principle involved in TLC is Adsorption, in which Stationary phase is solid and Mobile phase is liquid. It provides simultaneous analysis of samples in a relative shorter period.

Stationary phase: TLC plates (Silica gel G 60 F25)

The mobile phase used for analysis was Ammonium acetate: Acetone in the ratio of 9:1 respectively.

The observations obtained are presented. (Table 2)

UV- VISIBLE SPECTROSCOPY:

It is the basis for several ideal methods for determination of micro and semi-micro quantities of analytes of samples. The principle is mainly based on "BEER-LAMBERT LAW".

All the 09 SFCS standard solution of 10 μ g/ml was scanned in wavelength range of 200-800nm and the Absorption maxima was recorded and presented in Table 3.

VALIDATION OF UV-VISIBLE SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD:

Preparation of standard stock solution:

Standard stock solution (1000 μ g/ml) was prepared by transferring accurately weighed 10mg of 9 different

standard Synthetic food colours in 9 different 10ml volumetric flask and volume was made with distilled water.

Preparation of working stock solution:

0.1 ml of standard stock solution of 9 SFCs was withdrawn and transferred to 9 different 10ml volumetric flask, volume was made up to the mark with distilled water to get working standard solution of 10µg/ml of all 9 SFCs.

Preparation of sample solution:

1ml of sample was withdrawn from different marketed juice samples and transferred to 10ml volumetric flask; volume was made up to 10ml with distilled water.

LINEARITY:

Linearity was demonstrated for all the 9 standard SFCs using different concentration levels from 0.1µg/ml to 50µg/ml. The absorbance was recorded, and calibration plot was plotted using concentration of standard SFCs against absorbance.

Calibration curve for SFCs:

Appropriate volume of aliquots 0.001, 0.005, 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5ml from standard stock solution was transferred to 10 different volumetric flasks of 10 ml capacity. The volume was made up to the mark with water to obtain concentration of 0.1- 50µg/ml. The absorbance of standard SFCs was measured at λ_{\max} for each colour. The standard calibration curve was plotted and the data & chromatogram obtained is presented in **Table 3 & Fig 1-9**

ACCURACY:

The accuracy of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement between the value which is accepted either as a conventional true value or an acceptable reference value and the value found.

REPEATABILITY:

For repeatability studies, 0.1ml of standard stock solution was transferred into 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to the mark with distilled water to obtain concentration of 10µg/ml and analysed five times on the same day at same time. The absorbance was recorded and the %RSD was calculated and presented in **Table 5**.

INTRADAY AND INTERDAY

The intra and inter day studies were determined by measuring the absorbance at different time intervals on the same day and on 2 consecutive days (intraday precision) for 10µg/ml standard solution of 9 different SFCs. The absorbance was recorded and the %RSD was calculated and presented in **Table 5**.

LIMIT OF DETECTION (LOD):

LOD is the lowest amount analyte in a sample that can be detected but not necessarily quantified as an exact value.

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \sigma/S$$

LIMIT OF QUANTIFICATION (LOQ):

The quantification limit is a parameter of quantitative assays for low levels of compounds in sample which can be quantified.

$$\text{LOQ} = 10.0 \times \sigma/S$$

Where, S = Mean slope of five calibration curve values.

σ = Standard deviation of Y- intercepts.

LOD, LOQ and all calibration parameters¹⁴ were calculated from the linearity data and is presented in **Table 4**.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

TABLE 1: Observation for preliminary testing of 9 SFCs

Sl.no.	SFCs	Colour	Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Conc. HCl	NaOH	Methanol	NH ₃
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1.	Allura Red	Reddish brown	Very dark red	Very dark red	Dark red	Dark red	Dark red
2.	Carmoisine	Dark red	Pink at junction	Light orange red precipitate	Light red	Dark red	Dark red
3.	Ponceau 4R	Red	Not soluble	Red	Dark red	Red	Dark red
4.	Erythrosine	Pinkish red	Orange gelatinous	Orange	Pinkish red	Orange	Pinkish red
5.	Tartrazine	Yellow	Gelatinous ppt.	Dark yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Dark Yellow
6.	Sunset Yellow	Orange	Dark orange	Orange	Red	Light orange	Red
7.	Indigo carmine	Purplish blue	Immiscible	Purplish blue	Light green	Purplish blue	Light green
8.	Brilliant Blue	Blue	Blue	Green to yellow	Blue	Blue	Blue
9.	Fast green FCF	Brown-violet	Orange	Orange	Lemon green	blue	Turbid, colorless

Table 2: R_f value of SFCs in Standards and Samples by Paper Chromatography and TLC

SFCs	Paper Chromatography		Thin Layer Chromatography	
	R_f Value of Standard	R_f Value of Sample	R_f Value of Standard	R_f Value of Sample
Sunset Yellow	0.29	0.27	0.41	0.40
Ponceau 4R	0.32	0.31	0.28	0.27
Allura Red	0.30	0.29	0.68	0.65
Tartrazine	0.70	0.71	0.43	0.41
Brilliant Blue	0.71	0.69	0.64	0.65
Carmoisine	0.12	0.11	0.35	0.33
Erythrosine	0.02	0.021	0.46	0.42

RESULTS FOR VALIDATION OF UV-VISIBLE SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD:

Table 3: Absorption Maxima(λ_{max}) and Linearity data for 9 SFC

CON C($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}$)	ABSORBANCE								
	Allura Red	Tartrazine	Sunset Yellow	Brilliant Blue	Indigo Carmine	Carmoisine	Ponceau 4R	Erythrosine	Fast Green
λ_{max}	505 nm	427 nm	482 nm	629 nm	610 nm	516.3 nm	507 nm	526.3 nm	617 nm
0.1	0.004	0.008	0.001	0.024	0.006	0.013	0.007	0.015	0.026
0.5	0.022	0.016	0.022	0.049	0.015	0.021	0.026	0.044	0.046
1	0.036	0.03	0.036	0.092	0.033	0.043	0.034	0.084	0.086
2	0.075	0.063	0.075	0.187	0.067	0.085	0.075	0.17	0.187
3	0.104	0.086	0.097	0.273	0.091	0.122	0.104	0.266	0.267
5	0.147	0.145	0.157	0.428	0.152	0.207	0.16	0.45	0.452
10	0.327	0.285	0.357	0.876	0.384	0.391	0.295	0.859	0.855
20	0.769	0.660	0.867	1.875	0.754	0.833	0.680	1.718	1.696
30	1.184	1.014	1.302	2.939	1.087	1.259	1.03	2.466	3.386
50	2.075	1.599	2.405	-	1.689	2.122	1.745	4.00	3.674

FIG 1-9: Calibration Curve for 9 SFCs

Table 4: Calibration Parameters for 9 SFCs

Sl.no.	Colours	Slope	Y- intercept	R ²	LOD (µg/g)	LOQ(µg/g)
1.	Allura Red	0.0412	0.0272	0.9976	1.025	3.107
2.	Carmoisine	0.0423	0.0048	0.9997	0.342	1.03
3.	Ponceau 4R	0.0344	0.0033	0.9974	0.650	1.972
4.	Erythrosine	0.0804	0.029	0.9992	0.589	1.785
5.	Tartrazine	0.0325	0.0051	0.9984	1.34	4.06
6.	Sunset Yellow	0.0346	0.0071	0.9976	1.415	4.288
7.	Brilliant Blue	0.0969	0.0214	0.9984	0.859	2.603
8.	Indigo Carmine	0.0346	0.0071	0.9976	0.612	1.855
9.	Fast green	0.0819	0.0718	0.943	0.201	1.224

Table 5: Repeatability studies data and Interday, Intraday precision studies for 9 SFCs

SL. NO	SFCs	MEAN ABSORBANCE* (n=5)	SD	%RSD	INTERDAY %RSD*	INTRADAY %RSD*
1	Allura Red	0.313	0.001	0.319489	0.547819	0.492221
2	Carmoisine	0.3954	0.005857	1.481189	0.586639	0.932462
3	Ponceau 4R	0.2622	0.003493	1.332132	1.218482	0.646291
4	Erythrosine	0.8178	0.003114	0.380837	0.495074	0.52369
5	Tartrazine	0.2026	0.002408	1.188706	1.206645	0.693242
6	Sunset Yellow	0.354	0.003674	1.037919	1.29103	0.832356
7	Indigo Carmine	0.3798	0.00455	1.197927	1.140808	1.242546
8	Brilliant Blue	0.9094	0.005683	0.624951	0.539506	0.808281
9	Fast Green FCF	0.8626	0.004722	0.547448	0.407254	0.408993

*Average of five readings

ABSORBANCE OF SFCs IN STANDARDS AND MARKETED JUICE SAMPLES AT ANALYTICAL WAVELENGTH:

Table 6: Absorbance of SFCs at Analytical wavelength

Sl.no.	Max. wavelength	Standard SFCs	Std. Abs. (10µg/ml)	Sample	Absorbance
1.	505 nm	Allura red	0.407	AR-Sample	0.429
2.	516.3 nm	Carmoisine	0.357	C-Sample	0.188
3.	507 nm	Ponceau 4R	0.282	P-4R Sample	0.222
4.	526.3 nm	Erythrosine	0.823	E-Sample	0.202
5.	427 nm	Tartrazine	0.329	T- Sample	0.039
6	482 nm	Sunset Yellow	0.426	SY- Sample	0.380
7.	629 nm	Brilliant Blue	0.902	BB-Sample	0.068

Report: The Absorbance of Standard SFCs and SFCs present in the samples selected from market showed the absorbance at same analytical wavelength.

Table 7: observed limit of sfc in marketed juice samples.

SFCs	SAMPLES	OBSERVED ADI (mg/kg/d)	ADI (mg/kg/d) ^{11,13} ACCEPTABLE LIMIT*
SUNSET YELLOW (SY)	SY-1 Sample	1.55	3.75
	SY-2 Sample	1.13	3.75
	SY-3 Sample	1.29	3.75
	SY-4 Sample	2.47	3.75
	SY-5 Sample	3.09	3.75
ALLURA RED (AR)	AR-1 Sample	3.85	7
	AR-2 Sample	2.67	7
	AR-3 Sample	1.72	7
BRILLIANT BLUE (BB)	BB-1 Sample	0.062	6
	BB-2 Sample	0.36	6
	BB-3 Sample	0.22	6
	BB-4 Sample	0.140	6
PONCEAU 4R (P- 4R)	P-4R Sample	2.74	4
TARTRAZINE (T)	T-Sample	2.47	7.5
CARMOISINE (C)	C-Sample	3.266	4
ERYTHROSINE (E)	E-Sample	0.589	2.5

- ADI¹¹ as per US-FDA

Report: All the fruit juice samples collected from the market are within the acceptable daily intake limit of SFC as per US-FDA

CONCLUSION

The proposed UV Spectrophotometric method was developed successfully. All the validation parameters were validated as per ICH Guidelines. The linearity was performed on a series of concentration and was found to be linear in the range of 0.1-50 µg/ml. LOD & LOQ was calculated from linearity data and correlation coefficient (R^2) was found be greater than 0.997. The %RSD of precision was found be within the acceptance criteria of less than 2% indicating the

method was stable during the repeatability, intra and inter-day studies. Through a comprehensive review of existing literature, 9 synthetic food colours are permitted to be used within the acceptable range, beyond which they cause toxic effects such as allergy, hyperactivity and many more adverse reactions. Preliminary test, Paper chromatography and thin layer chromatography were performed to identify the 09 SFCs. The method effectiveness lies in its simplicity, cost- effectiveness, making it a valuable tool for quality control and regulatory compliance within the food industry. The amount of SFCs present in different fruit juices Samples in market were determined and the ADI was calculated and compared with the standard Acceptable limit given by US-FDA to know the amount of SFCs is below or beyond the limit. This study helped us to identify Fruit juices available in market with SFCs and to create awareness among children and youths on usage of marketed fruit juices containing SFCs and its adverse effects on human body

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